

Ru^{III}/Os^{VIII}/Ru^{III} + Os^{VIII} catalyzed Oxidation of Allyl Alcohol by Periodate in Aqueous Alkaline Medium

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Manuscript received 7 March 1996, revised 14 July 1997, accepted 23 October 1997

Kinetics of Ru^{III}/Os^{VIII}/Ru^{III} + Os^{VIII} catalyzed oxidation of allyl alcohol (AA) by periodate (IO₄⁻) in aqueous alkaline medium have been studied. The oxidation products are identified as acrolein and iodate in all cases. The order of [IO₄⁻] is found to be unity in all cases. The order of [AA] is found to be less than unity in all cases except in case of Os^{VIII} catalyzed reaction which is zero. Rate increases with increase in [OH⁻] in all cases. The orders of [Ru^{III}] and [Os^{VIII}] are unity in each case and less than unity each in case of Ru^{III} + Os^{VIII} catalyzed reaction. The catalytic efficiency follows the order : Ru^{III} < Os^{VIII} < Ru^{III} + Os^{VIII}. The probable mechanisms are discussed and reaction constants evaluated.

Kinetic studies on the oxidation of allyl alcohol with different oxidants have been reported¹. In alkaline medium, periodate is known to exist as different species involving multiple equilibria² and it needs to know the active form of the oxidant in the reaction.

In recent years, the use of transition metal ions, such as osmium, ruthenium and iridium either alone or as binary mixtures as catalysts³ in the oxidation of several redox processes is of considerable interest. The role of Os^{VIII} as a catalyst in some redox reactions has been reviewed⁴. Os^{VIII} and Ru^{III} catalysis in redox reactions involve several complexities⁵ due to formation of different intermediate complexes, different oxidation states of Ru/Os etc. Since allyl alcohol oxidation by periodate, both in presence or absence of either Ru^{III}, Os^{VIII} or Ru^{III} + Os^{VIII} does not take place in acid medium, we have investigated the kinetics of oxidation of allyl alcohol by periodate in presence of these metal ions as catalysts in alkaline medium in order to interpret the plausible mechanisms.

Results and Discussion

Under the experimental conditions [IO₄⁻] << [AA], the order in [IO₄⁻] was found to be unity in all cases, as indicated by the linearity of the plots of log [IO₄⁻] versus time to over more than three half-lives of the reaction and the constancy of rate constants at different concentrations of periodate at 25 ± 0.1°, unless otherwise stated.

The rate of reaction was found to increase with the increase in [AA] in case of Ru^{III} and Ru^{III} + Os^{VIII} catalyzed reactions and order with respect to [AA] was less than unity (Tables 1 and 3). However, in case of Os^{VIII} catalyzed reaction, the order in [AA] was found to be zero (Table 2). The rate of the reaction was accelerated by increasing [Ru^{III}] and order with respect to [Ru^{III}] was found to be unity (Table 1) in case of Ru^{III} catalyzed reaction,

while in case of Ru^{III} + Os^{VIII} catalyzed reaction at constant [Os^{VIII}], the order in [Ru^{III}] was found to be less than unity (Table 3). The rate of the reaction was increased by increasing [Os^{VIII}] and the order in [Os^{VIII}] was found to be unity (Table 2) in case of Os^{VIII} catalyzed reaction. However, in case of Ru^{III} + Os^{VIII} catalyzed reaction at constant [Ru^{III}], the order with respect to [Os^{VIII}] was less than unity (Table 3). The rate of the reaction was found to increase with increase in [OH⁻] at constant ionic strength, all other conditions being constant (Tables 1-3).

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF VARIATION OF [AA], [OH⁻] AND [Ru^{III}] ON Ru^{III}-CATALYZED OXIDATION OF AA BY PERIODATE

Temp. = 25°, [IO ₄ ⁻] = 4.0 × 10 ⁻³ , I = 0.60/mol dm ⁻³				
10 ² [AA] mol dm ⁻³	10[OH ⁻] mol dm ⁻³	10 ⁶ [Ru ^{III}] mol dm ⁻³	10 ⁵ k _c s ⁻¹	
			Exptl.	Calcd.
2.0	2.0	5.0	8.9	8.9
4.0	2.0	5.0	15.6	15.6
6.0	2.0	5.0	20.8	20.9
10.0	2.0	5.0	28.5	28.5
15.0	2.0	5.0	34.8	34.9
20.0	2.0	5.0	39.3	39.3
4.0	0.5	5.0	5.5	5.5
4.0	1.0	5.0	9.7	9.7
4.0	1.5	5.0	12.9	13.0
4.0	2.0	5.0	15.6	15.6
4.0	3.0	5.0	19.7	19.7
4.0	5.0	5.0	24.8	24.8
4.0	2.0	1.0	3.1	3.1
4.0	2.0	3.0	9.4	9.4
4.0	2.0	5.0	15.6	15.6
4.0	2.0	7.0	21.9	21.9
4.0	2.0	9.0	28.1	28.1
4.0	2.0	10.0	31.3	31.3

TABLE 2-EFFECT OF VARIATION OF [AA], [OH⁻] AND [Os^{VIII}] ON Os^{VIII} CATALYZED OXIDATION OF AA BY PERIODATE

Temp. = 25°, [IO₄⁻] = 4.0 × 10⁻³, I = 0.6 mol dm⁻³

10 ² [AA] mol dm ⁻³	10[OH ⁻] mol dm ⁻³	10 ⁶ [Os ^{VIII}] mol dm ⁻³	10 ⁴ k'	
			Exptl.	Calcd.
2.0	2.0	5.0	8.5	-
4.0	2.0	5.0	8.5	-
6.0	2.0	5.0	8.4	-
10.0	2.0	5.0	8.5	-
15.0	2.0	5.0	8.4	-
20.0	2.0	5.0	8.5	-
4.0	0.5	5.0	3.1	3.0
4.0	1.0	5.0	5.3	5.3
4.0	1.5	5.0	7.0	7.1
4.0	2.0	5.0	8.5	8.5
4.0	3.0	5.0	10.7	10.7
4.0	5.0	5.0	13.5	13.5
4.0	2.0	1.0	1.7	1.7
4.0	2.0	2.0	3.4	3.4
4.0	2.0	5.0	8.5	8.5
4.0	2.0	6.0	10.2	10.2
4.0	2.0	8.0	13.6	13.6
4.0	2.0	10.0	17.0	17.0

TABLE 3-EFFECT OF VARIATION OF [AA], [OH⁻], [Ru^{III}] AND [Os^{VIII}] ON Ru^{III} + Os^{VIII} CATALYZED OXIDATION OF ALLYL ALCOHOL BY PERIODATE

Temp. = 25°, [IO₄⁻] = 4.0 × 10⁻³, I = 0.60 mol dm⁻³

10 ² [AA] mol dm ⁻³	10[OH ⁻] mol dm ⁻³	10 ⁷ [Ru ^{III}] mol dm ⁻³	10 ⁷ [Ru ^{III}] mol dm ⁻³	10 ³ k'' s ⁻¹
2.0	2.0	5.0	5.0	1.5
4.0	2.0	5.0	5.0	2.5
6.0	2.0	5.0	5.0	3.0
10.0	2.0	5.0	5.0	3.3
15.0	2.0	5.0	5.0	3.9
20.0	2.0	5.0	5.0	4.3
4.0	0.5	5.0	5.0	1.2
4.0	1.0	5.0	5.0	1.4
4.0	1.5	5.0	5.0	1.7
4.0	2.0	5.0	5.0	2.5
4.0	3.0	5.0	5.0	3.3
4.0	5.0	5.0	5.0	3.9
4.0	2.0	1.0	5.0	1.1
4.0	2.0	2.0	5.0	1.8
4.0	2.0	5.0	5.0	2.5
4.0	2.0	7.0	5.0	3.1
4.0	2.0	9.0	5.0	3.5
4.0	2.0	10.0	5.0	4.0
4.0	2.0	5.0	1.0	1.5
4.0	2.0	5.0	2.0	2.1
4.0	2.0	5.0	5.0	2.5
4.0	2.0	5.0	7.0	3.5
4.0	2.0	5.0	9.0	4.3
4.0	2.0	5.0	10.0	5.4

The effect of change of dielectric constant of the medium on the reactions was studied by increasing the t-butanol content in reaction solution at constant concentrations of reactants and alkali, and at constant ionic strength. No significant change was observed. Increase in ionic

strength by addition of sodium perchlorate had no significant effect too. The initial addition of product IO₃⁻ and acrolein, each in the range of 1.0 × 10⁻³ to 8.0 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³, keeping all other conditions constant, did not affect the rate of reactions. To test for free radicals, the reaction mixtures containing acrylamide was kept for 24 h and then diluted with methanol. A copious precipitate resulted, indicating the presence of free radicals in all the cases.

In case of Ru^{III} catalyzed reaction, the rate constants (k₁) of the slow step (Scheme 1) were obtained from the slopes and intercepts of 1/k_C vs 1/[AA] and 1/k_C vs 1/[OH⁻] plots at four different temperatures and were used for the calculation of activation parameters (Table 4). In case of Os^{VIII} catalyzed reaction, the rate constants (k₂) of the slow step (Scheme 2) were obtained from the slopes and intercepts of 1/k' vs 1/[OH⁻] plots at different temperatures (Table 4). In case of Ru^{III} + Os^{VIII} catalysis, we could not evaluate the rate constant of the slow step of the reaction (Scheme 3) since the rate equation (4) involves many terms. Hence, temperature effect in this case with respect to slow step is not attempted.

TABLE 4-ACTIVATION PARAMETERS

Temp. °C	Ru ^{III} catalyzed reaction	Os ^{VIII} catalyzed reaction
	10 ² k ₁ dm ³ mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹	10 ² k ₂ dm ⁻³ mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹
25	3.3	4.4
30	4.8	5.9
35	6.5	7.4
40	8.7	9.2
ΔH [#]	46.02 ± 2.0	28.0 ± 2.0
ΔG [#]	59.0 ± 3.0	52.0 ± 2.0
ΔS [#]	-42.0 ± 2.0	-79.0 ± 4.0
ΔH [#] and ΔG [#] in kJ mol ⁻¹ ; ΔS [#] in J K ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹		

The activity of periodate as an oxidizing agent varies greatly as a function of pH. The nature of periodate ion in aqueous alkaline medium has received considerable attention. Periodic acid (H₅IO₆) exists in acid medium⁶ and also as H₄IO₆⁻ around pH 7.0. Thus, under the alkaline condition, the main species are expected to be H₃IO₆²⁻ and H₂IO₆³⁻. The observed fractional order in [OH⁻] in all the cases may be understood in terms of H₂IO₆³⁻ as main species in alkaline medium with the equilibrium,

Ru^{III} catalyzed reaction : Increase in rate with [OH⁻] indicates that the hydroxylated species of Ru^{III} is the active species⁷ of the catalyst in the reaction. Since [OH⁻] >> [Ru^{III}] it is assumed that all Ru^{III} is present as hydroxylated species (shown as Ru^{III*}). The results suggest that the complex formation between catalyst and substrate, which in turn reacts with oxidant species in the rate-determining step to give the free radical and I(vi) with regeneration of the catalyst, Ru^{III}. This slow step is subsequently followed by a

other intermediates such as I(vi) with regeneration of OsO₄. This slow step is further followed by another fast step to give the products.

As in case of Ru^{III} and Os^{VIII} catalyzed reactions, here also the active species of the catalysts are considered to be hydroxylated species of Ru^{III} ⁷ represented as Ru^{III*} and monohydroxy species of Os^{VIII} ^{10,11} written as OsO₄* (Scheme 3). The fractional order dependence of rate on [AA], [Ru^{III}] and [Os^{VIII}] shows that all these are involved in complex formation before the rate-determining step. The formation of complex (C_I) between substrate and OsO₄* is envisaged as the initial step. This complex (C_I) in the presence of Ru^{III*} would form another reactive intermediate complex (C_{II}) which is then assumed to interact with oxidant species in a slow step resulting in I(vi) and catalysts Os^{VIII} and Ru^{III} are regenerated. The subsequent fast step involves the formation of products, thus accounting for the 1 : 1 stoichiometry.

All these points may be incorporated in the mechanism shown in Scheme 3.

Scheme 3

The possible structures of C_I and C_{II} may be of the form,

The rate law based on Scheme 3 is given by equation (4),

$$\frac{\text{Rate}}{[\text{H}_3\text{IO}_6^{2-}]} = k'' = \frac{k_3 K_3 K_4 K_{\text{eq}} [\text{AA}]_T [\text{Ru}^{\text{III}}]_T [\text{Os}^{\text{VIII}}]_T [\text{OH}^-]_T}{\{1 + K_3 K_4 [\text{Os}^{\text{VIII}}] [\text{AA}]\} \{1 + K_3 [\text{AA}] + K_3 K_4 [\text{AA}] [\text{Ru}^{\text{III}}]\} \{1 + K_3 [\text{Os}^{\text{VIII}}]\} \{1 + K_{\text{eq}} [[\text{OH}^-]]\}} \quad (4)$$

The rate law (4) satisfactorily explains the observed kinetic results. The factor $(1 + K_{\text{eq}} [\text{H}_3\text{IO}_6^{2-}])$ is approximated to unity as compared to earlier results.

The negligible effect of ionic strength and dielectric constant on the rates of reaction in all cases may be understood to the presence of neutral species such as allyl alcohol in Schemes 1–3. The complex involved in the mechanisms of schemes in all three cases is expected to lead to a negative entropy of activation and this is found to be the case. The values of enthalpy of activation, free energy of activation and rate constant indicate the order of reactivity of the catalysts as $\text{Ru}^{\text{III}} < \text{Os}^{\text{VIII}} < \text{Ru}^{\text{III}} + \text{Os}^{\text{VIII}}$.

Experimental

All chemicals used were of A.R. grade. Double-distilled water was used throughout. The stock solutions of periodate were prepared by dissolving KIO₄ (Riedel) in water and used after keeping for 24 h, and standardized iodometrically¹⁴. Allyl alcohol (sd fine-chem) was purified by standard procedure and its concentration in aqueous solution was checked¹⁵ by addition of excess chloramine-T followed by iodometric titration. The Ru^{III} and Os^{VIII} solutions were prepared by dissolving RuCl₃ (sd fine-chem) in 0.20 mol dm⁻³ HCl and OsO₄ (Johnson Matthey) in 0.50 mol dm⁻³ NaOH. The concentration of Ru^{III} was ascertained¹⁷ by the addition of an excess Fe(CN)₆⁴⁻ followed by titration of unreacted Fe(CN)₆⁴⁻ with standard Ce^{IV} solution in acid medium. The IO₃ solution was prepared by dissolving KIO₃ (Reechem) in water. NaClO₄ and NaOH were used to maintain ionic strength and alkalinity respectively.

The kinetics were followed by withdrawing aliquots (5.0 ml) of the reaction mixture at regular intervals of time and added to distilled water and sufficient KH₂PO₄ just to neutralize the alkali and to bring pH of the solution to 5.0–5.5. The liberated iodine was titrated against standard thiosulphate solution using starch as an indicator. The initial rates were calculated by plane mirror method¹⁸ and pseudo-first order rate constant was calculated from log [IO₄] vs time plot. The orders were determined from logarithmic plots of initial rates versus reactant concentration except in case of Ru^{III} catalyzed reaction. As the IO₄ oxidation of AA in alkaline medium proceeds with measurable rate in the absence of Ru^{III}, the catalyzed reaction is understood to occur in parallel paths with contributions from both the catalyzed and uncatalyzed paths. Thus, the total rate constant (k_T) is equal to the sum of rate constants of catalyzed (k_C) and uncatalyzed (k_U) reactions. Thus, k_C = k_T - k_U. Hence in this case, the order of reaction was found from logarithmic plots of k_C vs concentrations. In case of Os^{VIII} catalyzed and Ru^{III} + Os^{VIII} catalyzed reactions, contribution from uncatalyzed reaction is negligible. Kinetic data were reproducible to within ±5%. Kinetic runs were followed for more than three half-lives of the reaction.

The stoichiometry of the reactants [AA] : [IO₄] was

NOTE

found to be 1 : 1 in all cases. Acrolein was found to be the main product as evidenced by the spot-test^{19,20} and test for acrylic acid was negative in all cases.

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